

1 **Fabrication of electrochemical sensor based on Eu₂O₃/rGO nanostructure for endocrine**
2 **disruptor estradiol sensing. Theoretical perspective on the sensing mechanism**

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18 **Abstract**

19 Accurate detection and monitoring of endocrine disruptor estradiol in clinical and environmental
20 contexts are crucial due to its implications for health and ecological systems. In this work, we
21 developed an electrochemical sensor based on europium oxide (Eu₂O₃) and reduced graphene
22 oxide (rGO) for quantification of estradiol in aqueous solutions. Eu₂O₃ synthesized using the
23 hydrothermal method formed ultrasmall and uniform nanoparticles and showed an efficient
24 electrochemical behavior. Eu₂O₃ nanoparticles were incorporated with rGO and characterized by
25 XRD, FTIR, SEM, and TEM. The obtained Eu₂O₃@rGO composite was drop-casted on the surface
26 of a screen-printed carbon electrode to construct a sensor for estradiol quantification. The
27 fabricated sensor exhibited an impressive limit of detection (0.06 μM) and a limit of quantification
28 (0.236 μM), with a sensitivity of 2.44 μA μM⁻¹ cm⁻², using SWV. The obtained SWV curve shows
29 the oxidation current increased during the addition of estradiol concentration from 0.1 to 30 μM.
30 The practical applicability of the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor was demonstrated for detecting
31 estradiol in tap water, river water, and saliva samples. The results obtained with the
32 SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor closely matched those from the UV-Vis validation method, confirming
33 its reliability and accuracy. The developed sensor represents a promising candidate for routine

34 environmental analysis due to its portability, lower cost, and potential for on-site and real-time
35 monitoring.

36 **Keywords:**

37 Rare earth element, endocrine disruptor, voltammetry, electrochemical sensor, Density Functional
38 Theory

39 **Introduction**

40 Estradiol (E2), the foremost estrogen hormone, regulates reproductive and non-reproductive
41 physiological processes in humans and animals. As a major estrogen, estradiol helps the formation
42 and maintenance of female reproductive tissues, bone density, and cardiovascular health [1].
43 Besides, estradiol is a biomarker for several illnesses in human health, such as infertility, and
44 hormone-related malignancies. Hormone-sensitive cancers, including ovarian and breast cancer,
45 or endocrine problems may be indicated by abnormal estradiol levels [2-3]. Beyond its biomedical
46 relevance, estradiol is increasingly recognized as an emerging environmental contaminant due to
47 its classification as an endocrine-disrupting compound, capable of altering endocrine functions in
48 both animals and humans. It primarily enters aquatic ecosystems through wastewater discharge,
49 encompassing effluents from pharmaceutical manufacturing, healthcare facilities, and agricultural
50 runoff containing animal waste. The presence of estradiol in aquatic environments presents
51 significant risks to aquatic life, particularly by disrupting reproductive processes, which may result
52 in reduced fertility and ecological imbalances. Therefore, rigorous monitoring of estradiol levels
53 in water systems is essential to mitigate potential environmental and ecological hazards [4-5].
54 Conventional methods for detecting estradiol, including high-performance liquid chromatography
55 (HPLC) and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA), provide excellent sensitivity and
56 specificity. However, these techniques are often associated with high costs, lengthy analysis times,
57 and intricate sample preparation procedures [6]. Therefore, a new, accurate, rapid, and affordable
58 method for the detection and monitoring of estradiol in clinical and environmental samples is
59 urgently needed for health and environmental applications.

60 In recent years, sensor-based technologies have gained significant attention as a promising
61 alternative for estradiol detection, offering rapid, cost-efficient, and on-site monitoring
62 capabilities. The advancement of innovative sensors aims to overcome the drawbacks of traditional
63 techniques while improving the effectiveness of monitoring in diverse matrices such as biological

64 fluids and environmental water sources [7]. Because of their unique electrical, optical, and
65 catalytic properties, rare-earth metal oxides have piqued the curiosity of electrochemists. Their
66 exceptional stability and great electrical conductivity make them ideal for electrochemical sensors
67 and systems. Notably, rare-earth oxides can improve electron transport kinetics at electrode
68 surfaces, increasing sensitivity while decreasing response time in electrochemical systems.
69 Including these materials into electrochemical systems shows great potential for real-time
70 monitoring and detection, especially in environmental and medicinal applications [8-9].

71 Eu_2O_3 was selected due to its favorable electrocatalytic and surface properties. Europium stands
72 out among lanthanides for its pronounced redox behavior and catalytic potential. The surface of
73 Eu_2O_3 contains a variety of reactive sites that enhance both adsorption and catalysis. Importantly,
74 Eu_2O_3 remains stable in the Eu^{3+} oxidation state under typical sensing conditions, while its inherent
75 oxygen vacancies (structural defects) can act as active sites for analyte adsorption and facilitate
76 electron and proton transfer during redox reactions [10-12]. These characteristics contribute to
77 richer surface chemistry compared to many conventional metal oxides, ultimately improving both
78 the activity and selectivity of the sensor. For phenolic analytes such as estradiol, this translates into
79 enhanced molecular recognition and a stronger electrochemical signal.

80 Reduced graphene oxide (rGO) has become a compelling material in electrochemistry, primarily
81 due to its outstanding electrical conductivity, expansive surface area, and abundance of surface
82 functional groups. Its distinctive structure—comprising several layers of sp^2 -hybridized carbon
83 atoms interspersed with residual oxygen-containing groups—offers a high density of active sites
84 for electrochemical reactions. Moreover, the large surface area of rGO enhances the electrode's
85 ability to adsorb analytes, thereby improving detection sensitivity and selectivity [13-14].

86 In this study, estradiol was detected for the first time using a modified screen-printed carbon
87 electrode (SPCE) with Eu_2O_3 nanoparticles and rGO composite. The synergistic combination of
88 Eu_2O_3 and rGO in the SPCE/ Eu_2O_3 @rGO sensor enhances electrochemical performance by
89 integrating the excellent conductivity and high surface area of rGO with the redox activity of
90 Eu_2O_3 . This interaction improves electron transfer, analyte adsorption, and overall sensor
91 sensitivity, making it a highly effective platform for E2 detection in environmental and biomedical
92 applications. The method demonstrated high selectivity and sensitivity in detecting E2 in water
93 and human saliva samples, with results validated with the standard UV/Vis method.

94 **Experimental**

95 *Chemicals and instrumentation*

96 *Materials*

97 Europium (III) nitrate pentahydrate ($\text{Eu}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), potassium
98 ferrocyanide ($\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$), potassium ferricyanide ($\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$), potassium chloride (KCl),
99 sodium sulfide (Na_2S), graphene oxide (GO), potassium hydroxide (KOH), potassium chloride
100 (KCl), sodium nitrite (NaNO_2), sodium nitrate (NaNO_3), calcium chloride (CaCl_2), magnesium
101 chloride (MgCl_2), dopamine, ascorbic acid, uric acid, caffeine, threonine and estradiol were
102 obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and directly used for the experimental investigations without
103 purification.

104 Britton–Robinson buffer solution (BRBS) was prepared as a supporting electrolyte by mixing
105 equimolar amounts of phosphoric, acetic, and boric acids (40 mM). NaOH solution (0.2 M) was
106 used for adjusting the pH values of the buffer. A pH meter equipped with a universal glass
107 electrode (Orion 1230, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) was used for all
108 pH measurements. For the preparation of all solutions, double-distilled water was used.

109 *Electrochemical investigations*

110 For electrochemical measurements (cyclic voltammetry (CV), square wave voltammetry (SWV)),
111 the potentiostat/galvanostat PalmSens, model 4 (PalmSens BV, Vleugelboot 22, 3991 CL Houten
112 The Netherlands) was used. A classical three-electrode system with a (un)modified SPCE as the
113 working electrode (WE), a platinum plate as a counter electrode (CE), and Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) as
114 a reference electrode (RE) was used.

115 *IR-spectroscopy and XRD analysis*

116 After the visual impression and the analysis of the products based exclusively on the product yield,
117 the powders were analyzed using both infrared spectroscopy (IR) and powder diffraction (XRD).
118 The Alpha-T IR device, manufactured by BRUKER[®], was employed for IR spectroscopy. Before
119 commencing the measurements, the ATR crystal of the device was subjected to a cleaning process.
120 Subsequently, approximately 5 mg of the synthesized powder was positioned on the crystal and
121 pressed onto it using a stamp. The recorded values were obtained at wavenumbers ranging from
122 4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} with a step size of approximately $2,06\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

123 The powder diffraction experiments were conducted using devices manufactured by Panalytical.
124 The samples were analyzed on two distinct devices manufactured by the same company, both of
125 which were of the Empyrean type. A Cu Ka X-ray source (wavelengths: Ka1 = 1, 5405980 Å, Ka2
126 = 1, 5444260 Å) and a PIXcel1D detector (Panalytical) with 255 measuring channels were used.
127 The XRD measurement was carried out in the angular range from 10° to 90° with a step size of
128 0,0262606°.

129 *SEM and TEM analysis*

130 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS)
131 were performed using a FEI Helios NanoLab 660 SEM/FIB dual-beam system.

132 A JEOL JEM 2100 microscope was utilized for TEM investigation, operating at an accelerating
133 voltage of 120 kV for all measurements. To prepare the sample, a TEM grid was positioned in a
134 snap-lid jar containing the powder for analysis. The powder was subsequently agitated to facilitate
135 its deposition onto the grid. The biggest particles were eliminated by agitating the sample outside
136 the snap-lid container.

137 *Materials preparation*

138 *Synthesis of Eu₂O₃ nanoparticles*—The nanoparticles of Eu₂O₃ were synthesized using the
139 hydrothermal method, following literature procedure with minor modification [15]. The first
140 solution was prepared by dissolving 4×10^{-4} mol (0.1941 g) of Eu(NO₃)₃ x 5H₂O in 1 mL of distilled
141 water. A second solution was prepared by dissolving 1.68g of NaOH in 7 mL of distilled water (to
142 obtain a 6M solution), and these two solutions were mixed at room temperature and stirred for 30
143 minutes. After the formation of the milky slurry, the reaction mixture was transferred to a stainless-
144 steel vessel autoclave for 24 hours at 100°C. After cooling to room temperature, the precipitate
145 was centrifuged and washed three times with distilled water and ethanol. Finally, the product was
146 calcinated for 6 hours at 450°C. To modify the electrode, a suspension of Eu₂O₃ in DMF was
147 prepared with a concentration of 1 mg/mL. The suspension was subjected to ultrasonic treatment
148 for 1 hour, after which it was ready for use.

149 *Synthesis of rGO* – The synthesis of rGO was carried out according to the referenced procedure,
150 using ten times smaller amounts of reagents [16]. Briefly, 0.3 g of graphite was added to 7 mL of
151 concentrated sulfuric acid under continuous stirring at room temperature. Afterward, 0.15 g of
152 sodium nitrate was introduced, and the mixture was cooled to 0 °C. Under vigorous stirring, 0.9 g

153 of potassium permanganate was gradually added, ensuring the reaction temperature remained
154 below 20 °C. The mixture was then transferred to a water bath at 35–40 °C and maintained for 30
155 minutes, forming a dense paste. Subsequently, 14 mL of water was added, and the system was
156 stirred for an additional 15 minutes, followed by dilution with 50 mL of water and the slow addition
157 of 2 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30%), which turned the mixture from brown to yellow. The product
158 was filtered and washed sequentially with 25 mL of 1:10 diluted hydrochloric acid and deionized
159 water, then centrifuged repeatedly to eliminate residual acids. The obtained solid was redispersed
160 in water using ultrasonication for 1 hour to yield a 0.5 wt% GO suspension. The dispersion was
161 centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 30 minutes to remove aggregates and further purified by dialysis for
162 7 days to eliminate residual salts. For reduction to rGO, 0.1–0.2 mg/mL GO aqueous suspensions
163 were prepared, to which Na₂S solution (5.4 mmol/L) was added. The mixture was then heated at
164 90 °C for 3 hours without stirring. The resulting graphene hydrogel was thoroughly washed with
165 deionized water and ethanol to remove unreacted components and residual salts. A suspension of
166 rGO in DMF was prepared for easier modification of working electrodes, with a final concentration
167 of 1 mg mL⁻¹. The suspension was subjected to ultrasonic treatment for 1 hour and was
168 subsequently ready for use. A suspension of rGO in DMF was prepared for easier modification of
169 working electrodes, with a final concentration of 1 mg mL⁻¹. The suspension was subjected to
170 ultrasonic treatment for 1 hour and was subsequently ready for use.

171 *Fabrication of Eu₂O₃@rGO nanocomposite* – To synthesize the Eu₂O₃/rGO composite, 0.5 mg of
172 np-Eu₂O₃ was mixed with 0.5 mg of rGO and dissolved in DMF, resulting in a final composite
173 concentration of 1 mg mL⁻¹. The composite was subjected to ultrasonic treatment for 2 hours to
174 facilitate the incorporation of nanoparticles into the rGO structure.

175 ***Electrode modification***

176 Before each electrochemical measurement, every individual SPCE was activated using an identical
177 procedure. The electrodes underwent cyclic voltammetry in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ at a scan rate of 100 mV
178 s⁻¹ for 50 cycles to enhance surface functionality and remove impurities.

179 To compare the electrocatalytic properties of the synthesized materials and composites, four
180 working electrodes were prepared with the following labels: SPCE, SPCE/Eu₂O₃, SPCE/rGO, and
181 SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO. The working electrodes were modified by applying different amounts of
182 material. For each material intended for SPCE modification, a dispersion was prepared in DMF at

183 a final concentration of 1 mg/mL. Subsequently, aliquots of 2.5, 5, and 10 μ L were drop-cast onto
184 the working area of the SPCEs and left to dry overnight under ambient conditions to ensure
185 complete solvent evaporation prior to use.

186 *Preparation of standard curve for the UV method*

187 A parallel analysis of real samples was conducted using spectrophotometric measurements to
188 validate the application of the proposed electroanalytical method. The analysis was performed with
189 minor modifications to the referenced procedure [17]. The wavelength selected for E2 detection
190 was 280.75 nm. The calibration curve was prepared from a standard stock solution of E2 by
191 dissolving an appropriate amount of E2 in methanol. From this stock, standard working solutions
192 were obtained to achieve final concentrations of 4-20 μ M in 10 mL volumetric flasks by
193 appropriate dilution.

194 *Preparation of the real sample*

195 The proposed SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor and the developed electroanalytical method were
196 employed to determine E2 in tap water, river water, and human saliva samples. Tap water samples
197 were collected in Belgrade, Serbia, and stored at 4°C in a refrigerator prior to analysis. Before the
198 measurements, the samples were diluted tenfold with BRBS solution (pH = 4) and analyzed
199 directly. River water was sampled from the Danube River (Zemun, Serbia) and similarly stored at
200 4°C. Before electroanalytical measurements, the samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5
201 minutes to remove suspended particles, and the filtrate was further passed through a 0.45 μ m filter.
202 The processed samples were then diluted tenfold with BRBS solution (pH = 4) and analyzed
203 directly. Saliva samples were gathered from two healthy volunteers (one male and one female) at
204 least one hour post-meal after thoroughly rinsing their mouths with water. The samples were
205 collected in 1.5-mL tubes and stored at -20 °C until further use. Sample preparation for
206 electrochemical testing involved centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 30 minutes, filtration through a
207 0.45 μ m filter, and subsequent tenfold dilution with BRBS solution (pH = 4). For
208 spectrophotometric analysis, the samples were prepared in the same manner.

209 **Results and discussion**

210 *Structural analysis*

211 **Figure 1** show SEM micrographs of the used not yet exfoliated (prior to sonication) rGO (A), the
212 prepared Eu_2O_3 powder (B) and of the Eu_2O_3 @rGO composite material (C). Figure 1C
213 demonstrates the successful formation of the Eu_2O_3 @rGO composite, where Eu_2O_3 nanorods are
214 evenly distributed and well-adhered to the rGO matrix, indicating good dispersion and interaction.
215 The Eu_2O_3 particles exhibit an elongated form with a length of 300-1000 nm and a thickness of
216 50-100 nm (**Figure 1D**). Figure 1E and 1F illustrate the intimate contact between Eu_2O_3 and the
217 exfoliated rGO nanosheets. The Eu_2O_3 rods are clearly anchored onto single rGO sheets, which
218 supports good interfacial adhesion and suggests favorable electron transfer properties.

219
220 **Figure 1.** SEM micrographs of A) the used not yet exfoliated rGO (prior to sonication), B) the
221 prepared Eu_2O_3 powder and C) of the Eu_2O_3 @rGO composite material; TEM pictures of D) Eu_2O_3
222 powder E) Eu_2O_3 @rGO and F) magnification of Eu_2O_3 @rGO

223
224 The FT-IR spectrum of GO exhibits characteristic peaks at $\sim 1720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O stretching),
225 $\sim 1220\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-O-C stretching), and broad -OH vibrations in the $3200\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range,

226 confirming the presence of oxygen-containing functional groups. Upon reduction to rGO, these
227 bands significantly decrease in intensity, indicating successful deoxygenation. The spectrum of
228 Eu_2O_3 shows a strong absorption band near 545 cm^{-1} , corresponding to Eu–O vibrations. In the
229 composite material ($\text{Eu}_2\text{O}_3@\text{rGO}$), both Eu–O bands and residual oxygen functionalities from rGO
230 are present, suggesting successful integration of metal oxide onto the carbon surface, while
231 preserving key vibrational features. These observations confirm the formation of a stable hybrid
232 structure [17-18]

233 The XRD diffractogram (*Error! Reference source not found. Figure 2B*) shows all major Eu_2O_3
234 peaks compared to the reference as deposited at the International Centre for Diffraction Data
235 (ICDD database record no. 00-034-0392) with some small additional peaks between 20 and 30° .
236 The XRD pattern of Eu_2O_3 corresponds well with the standard ICDD database record no. 00-034-
237 0392, confirming the cubic crystalline phase with space group Ia-3 (no. 206). The most intense
238 peak at $2\theta \approx 28.43^\circ$ is assigned to the (222) reflection, with a calculated interplanar spacing (d) of
239 3.137 \AA using Bragg's law. These results are consistent with values obtained from TEM images
240 of the composite (Figure 1F), where the lattice fringe distance is also around 0.31 nm .

241

242

243 **Figure 2.** A) FT-IR spectrum of the pristine Eu_2O_3 powder; B) XRD patterns of Eu_2O_3 powder
244 and the reference material as deposited at the International Centre for Diffraction Data (ICDD
245 database record no. 00-034-0392)

246 *Exploring electrochemical insights*

247 The main objective of this study was to develop an SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor for the detection of
248 E2 in water samples.

249 *Optimization of nanocomposite amount added to SPCE*

250 Optimization of the amount of nanocomposite added to the SPCE was performed by cyclic
251 voltammetry. In this experiment, the electrochemical responses of SPCEs modified with 2.5 μL , 5
252 μL , and 10 μL of 1 mg mL⁻¹ Eu₂O₃, rGO, and Eu₂O₃@rGO nanocomposite were compared. The
253 effect of the amount of added material on the working electrode was investigated in a solution of
254 5 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} in 0.1 M KCl at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹.

255 Based on the obtained results presented in *Figure S1*, it was concluded that the optimal amount is
256 10 μL for SPCE/ rGO, 5 μL for SPCE/Eu₂O₃, and 2.5 μL for the composite. Further
257 electrochemical investigations were conducted using the specified quantities of the modified
258 SPCEs.

259 *Evaluating the electrocatalytic efficiency of working electrodes*

260 The electrocatalytic properties of the modified electrodes were analyzed using electrochemical
261 impedance spectroscopy (EIS) in a 0.1 M KCl solution containing 5 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-}.
262 Measurements were performed at a potential of 0 V, with a frequency range spanning from 0.01
263 Hz to 100 kHz. The resulting impedance data were modeled using the Randles equivalent circuit,
264 as illustrated in the inset of *Figure 3A*, where R_{ct} denotes charge transfer resistance, R_s indicates
265 electrolyte resistance, Z_w corresponds to Warburg impedance, and C_{dl} represents double-layer
266 capacitance. The semicircular part of the Nyquist plot illustrates the charge transfer limitations,
267 whereas the extended linear region reflects the diffusion-limited process. The diameter of the
268 semicircle is typically used to quantify the electrode's charge transfer resistance. The recorded R_{ct}
269 values were 4870 Ω , 3434 Ω , 2699 Ω , and 2313 Ω for SPCE, SPCE/Eu₂O₃, SPCE/rGO, and
270 SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO, respectively. The results indicate that the composite material successfully
271 reduced the electron transfer resistance by 2.105 times, which can be explained by the synergistic
272 properties of Eu₂O₃, such as its high surface-to-volume ratio, ultra-small particle size, and the
273 enhanced number of adsorptive sites provided by rGO, which significantly increases the active
274 surface area. Therefore, the novel composite is a highly promising material for electrochemical

275 sensing applications. Furthermore, a charge transfer rate (K_s) was determined using the following
276 Equation (Eq.). 1:

$$277 \quad K_s = \frac{RT}{n^2 F^2 R_{ct} C} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

278 where R is the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), T is the temperature of the reaction, n is
279 the number of the electrons transferred in the reaction, F is Faraday's constant (96485 C mol^{-1}),
280 and C represents the concentration of the redox couple. Calculated K_s values are $1.09 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$,
281 $1.55 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, $1.97 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, and $2.30 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ for SPCE, SPCE/ Eu_2O_3 , SPCE/ rGO, and
282 SPCE/ Eu_2O_3 @rGO, respectively. These values demonstrate that K_s increases as R_{ct} decreases,
283 which is expected since lower resistance indicates faster charge transfer. This further confirms the
284 enhanced electrocatalytic response of the newly synthesized material [19].

285 The electrocatalytic performance of the modified electrode was further examined through cyclic
286 voltammetry (CV) in a 0.1 M KCl solution containing 5 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ as the redox probe
287 (**Figure 3B**). The measurements were conducted at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} within a potential
288 range of -0.2 to 1.0 V . When compared to the bare SPCE, the modified electrodes exhibited the
289 greater redox peak current value in the observation of the CV findings. Compared to other
290 electrodes (SPCE, SPCE/rGO, SPCE/ Eu_2O_3), SPCE/ Eu_2O_3 @rGO exhibits a notably smaller redox
291 peak separation (ΔE_p) of 135 mV , along with a higher current response. In contrast, the redox peak
292 separations for the other modified electrodes are SPCE (267 mV), SPCE/ Eu_2O_3 (233 mV), and
293 SPCE/rGO (210 mV).

294 The impact of the mentioned synergy on the electrocatalytic activity of this material was
295 additionally clarified by the calculation of the electroactive surface area (EASA). Figure S2.
296 depicts scan rate (10 - 200 mV s^{-1}) examinations of bare SPCE, SPCE/ Eu_2O_3 , SPCE/rGO, and
297 SPCE/ Eu_2O_3 @rGO in 5 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ solution. The linear correlation was obtained between
298 the current and the square root of the scan rate. EASA of all working electrodes was calculated
299 using Randles-Sevcik Eq. (2) [20]:

$$300 \quad I_p = (2.69 \times 10^5) \times A \times n^{2/3} \times D^{1/2} \times C \times \nu^{1/2} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

301 where A denotes the electroactive surface area of the electrode, n is the number of transferred
302 electrons, D represents the diffusion coefficient, ν is the scan rate, and I_p depicts the peak current.
303 The EASA values for SPCE, SPCE/ Eu_2O_3 , SPCE/rGO, and SPCE/ Eu_2O_3 @rGO were calculated to
304 be 0.0373 , 0.0436 , 0.0454 , and 0.05173 cm^2 , respectively. These results indicate that

305 SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO exhibits the highest EASA value among the modified electrodes. The larger
306 surface area of the proposed SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO nanocomposite, which offered an enhanced
307 electrode–electrolyte interface for the accumulation of charged species and improved electron
308 transferability, was the primary cause of the higher redox current response of SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO
309 during electrocatalysis.

310 Determining the heterogeneous rate constant (*j*₀) is of critical importance in electrochemical
311 studies of materials, as it provides valuable insight into the intrinsic kinetics of electron transfer at
312 the electrode/electrolyte interface [21]. The exchange current density (*j*₀) of the reaction was
313 calculated using the following Eq. 3:

$$314 \quad j_0 = \frac{RT}{nFARct} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

315 with already-explained symbols. Additional confirmation of the superior performance of the
316 composite material, compared to the other tested materials, is provided by the calculated *j*₀ values
317 (A cm⁻²), which are as follows: 141.4 μA cm⁻² for SPCE, 171.5 μA cm⁻² for SPCE/Eu₂O₃, 209.6
318 μA cm⁻² for SPCE/rGO, and 214.6 μA cm⁻² for SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO.

319 The calculated effective electrode surface area was utilized to determine the surface coverage and
320 surface concentration of electroactive species on the modified electrode, employing the Brown-
321 Anson Eq. 4 [22]:

$$322 \quad I_{pa} = \frac{n^2 F^2 C A v}{4RT} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

323 where *F* is the Faraday constant (96500 C mol⁻¹), *n* is the number of electrons transferred (*n*=1), *A*
324 is the electrode surface area, *R* is the universal gas constant (8.314 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹), *I*_{pa} is the oxidation
325 current, *C* is the surface concentration of the absorbed electroactive species and *v* is the scan rate
326 (20 mVs⁻¹). From this equation, the surface concentrations of electroactive species of the working
327 electrode were evaluated to be 0.4939 x10⁻⁸ mol dm⁻², 0.5274 x10⁻⁸ mol dm⁻², 0.5583 x 10⁻⁸ mol
328 dm⁻², 0.6513 x 10⁻⁸ mol dm⁻² for SPCE, SPCE/Eu₂O₃, SPCE/ rGO, and SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO,
329 respectively. From this, it can be concluded that SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO has a high surface area and
330 permits a large degree of coverage by the electroactive species. This could ease the promotion of
331 the mass and ions transportation towards the target.

332 The SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO electrode exhibited a low charge transfer resistance (*R*_{ct}), a high
333 electrochemically active surface area, and an efficient surface concentration of electroactive

334 species. Additionally, the enhanced surface concentration of electroactive species contributed to
 335 increased current density toward the target. These features improved the electrocatalytic
 336 performance, making SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO a promising candidate for use as an electrochemical
 337 sensor for E2 detection.

338
 339 **Figure 3.** A) EIS spectra of bare SPCE; SPCE@rGO; SPCE/Eu₂O₃; SPCE/ rGO@Eu₂O₃ in redox
 340 probe of 5 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} in 0.1 M KCl solution. (Inset: Randles Equivalent circuit image);
 341 B) CV response of bare SPCE; SPCE@rGO; SPCE/Eu₂O₃; SPCE/rGO@Eu₂O₃ at a scan rate
 342 50 mV s⁻¹; C) CV responses of SPCE/rGO@Eu₂O₃ at different pH (3.0-9.0) of BRBS at a scan rate
 343 50 mV s⁻¹; D) The corresponding linear plot for different pH (3.0-9.0) versus potential and current;
 344 E) CV response of SPCE/rGO@Eu₂O₃ in 100 μM of E2 at different scan rates (5-50 mV s⁻¹) in
 345 BRBS at pH 4.0

346 **Electrochemical behavior of E2 on the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor**

347 To efficiently detect E2 in water samples using SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO, it is crucial to investigate the
 348 nature of the electrode process on the proposed sensor. For this matter, the working electrodes
 349 functionalized by different materials were compared regarding their E2 detection capabilities in
 350 buffer solution using the CV method, with a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ (**Figure 3C**). The CV results

351 obtained in 100 μM E2 solution in a BRBS at pH 4 revealed that the unmodified SPCE exhibited
352 the lowest anodic current response ($I = 2.95 \mu\text{A}$), which can be attributed to inefficient charge
353 transfer between the working electrode and E2. The incorporation of Eu_2O_3 nanoparticles, known
354 for their high electron transfer rate and exceptional dielectric properties, significantly enhanced
355 the oxidation peak current ($I = 4.495 \mu\text{A}$). In contrast, the electrode modified with rGO
356 demonstrated an increase in the oxidation peak current ($I = 6.391 \mu\text{A}$), which is explained by the
357 expansion of the active surface area. Furthermore, the $\text{Eu}_2\text{O}_3@\text{rGO}$ composite material exhibited
358 superior performance due to its remarkable electrocatalytic properties attributed to the large
359 surface area, high electrical conductivity, low R_{ct} , numerous active sites, and efficient charge
360 transport between the electrode and electrolyte interface. This was evidenced by an oxidation
361 current response of $I = 8.47 \mu\text{A}$, nearly three times higher than the bare SPCE. This enhancement
362 highlights the beneficial impact of $\text{Eu}_2\text{O}_3@\text{rGO}$ on electrode performance, likely attributed to the
363 unique properties of the material. The interaction between rGO and Eu_2O_3 significantly enhances
364 the electrocatalytic properties of the composite. rGO provides a highly conductive network that
365 facilitates rapid electron transfer, while Eu_2O_3 offers active redox sites for estradiol oxidation. The
366 intimate contact between the two phases, supported by residual defect sites and π - π interactions,
367 improves charge transport and analyte adsorption. This synergy results in increased current
368 response, lower overpotential and enhanced sensitivity of the sensor platform.

369 *Key factors influencing the electrochemical oxidation of E2: pH variations and scan rate* 370 *analysis*

371 *Investigating the impact of pH on electrochemical behavior*

372 The pH value of the supporting electrolyte significantly influences the electrochemical behavior
373 of the analyte, making it an essential parameter in electrocatalytic studies. To investigate this,
374 cyclic voltammetry was performed at pH ranging from 3.0 to 9.0, with a constant sweep rate of 50
375 mV s^{-1} . The oxidation peak current increases as the pH decreases from 3.0 to 9.0, accompanied by
376 a shift in the oxidation potential towards more negative values (**Figure 3D**). The highest current
377 response was detected at pH 4.0, while at pH 9.0, the current diminished, and the potential shift
378 became more pronounced. These variations can be attributed to protonation and deprotonation
379 reactions occurring at lower and higher pH values. Additionally, a strong linear relationship
380 between E_p and pH was observed across the range of pH 3.0 to 9.0 (**Figure 3E**), as expressed by

381 the following equation: $E_{p_a} = 0.663 - 0.056 \times \text{pH}$, with $R^2 = 0.990$. The obtained slope value was
382 used in the Nernst equation:

$$383 \quad E_p = - \left(\frac{0.0591 m}{n} \right) \text{pH} + b \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

384 where m and n are the number of protons and electrons, respectively. The slope of the curve, 56
385 mV, is very close to the theoretical Nernstian slope of 59 mV at 25°C, suggesting that an equal
386 number of protons and electrons participate in the oxidation of E2 on the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO
387 sensor. This observation aligns with previous reports [23-25]. Therefore, pH 4.0 was the optimal
388 pH for the supporting electrolyte solution, providing the highest oxidation peak current, and it was
389 chosen for further studies.

390 *Impact of scan rate on electrochemical performance*

391 The influence of scan rate on the redox peak characteristics of E2 was examined using CV assays
392 to analyze mass transport within the diffusion layer and determine the nature of the associated
393 redox process. The electrochemical behavior of 100 μM E2 in BRBS at pH 4 at various scan rates
394 (5–50 mV s⁻¹) is depicted in **Figure 3F**. When the scan rate was higher than 50 mV s⁻¹, the peak
395 shape and reproducibility were poor. The SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor exhibited a linear increase in
396 current response (I_{p_a}) for all redox peaks across the applied scan rate (v) range. The linearity
397 diagram of scan rate vs current response was shown in **Figure S3A**. The linear dependence was
398 given by the following equation: $I (\mu\text{A}) = 1.79 + 0.068 \times V (\text{mVs}^{-1})$ with $R^2 = 0.992$. These findings
399 suggest that the analyte's electrochemical processes at the electrode surface are predominantly
400 governed by adsorption rather than diffusion. Furthermore, the linear correlation obtained between
401 the log scan rate vs E_p is given in **Figure S3B**. The linear dependence was given by the following
402 equation: $E (\text{V}) = 0.24 + 0.136 \times \log V (\text{mVs}^{-1})$ with $R^2 = 0.990$, and it was used to calculate the
403 number of electrons transferred via the Laviron (1979) equation [26]:

$$404 \quad E_{p_a} = E^0 + \frac{2.3 R \times T}{(1 - \alpha) \times n \times F} \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

405 Where, R, T, F, n, and α (0.5 for irreversible process) are represented as universal gas constant,
406 temperature, Faraday constant, number of electrons transferred during the oxidation reaction, and
407 electron transfer coefficient, respectively. Then, E_{p_a} and E_o are denoted as anodic current
408 potential, and formal potential was calculated using dependence of the log scan rate on E_p . From
409 the slopes of the equation, the number of electrons transferred (n) can be calculated as $0.86 \approx 1$.

410 *Theoretical investigation*

411 *Computational details*

412 The entirety of the results presented herein were derived using the Gaussian 09 [27] electronic
413 structure program suite (Revision A.02) by using the Density Functional Theory (DFT)
414 methodology [28-29]. The computational analyses were executed utilizing the B3LYP [30-31]
415 density functional approximation in conjunction with the 6-311++G** [32] orbital basis set for all
416 atoms. In an effort to enhance calculation accuracy, the solvation effects of water have been
417 included using the polarizable conductor continuum model (C-PCM) through the solvent cavity
418 reaction field (SCRF) method [33]. The mentioned computational conditions were applied for full
419 optimization and corresponding theoretical investigation.

420 *Theoretical modeling of the experiment*

421 To elucidate the mechanisms underlying the electrochemical behavior of E2, a theoretical
422 investigation of its redox properties was carried out, beginning from the fully relaxed ground-state
423 electron density. From a theoretical standpoint, oxidation is expected to primarily affect the highest
424 occupied molecular orbital (HOMO), while reduction predominantly involves the lowest
425 unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO). The structure and spatial distribution of the HOMO,
426 shown in *Figure 4A*, together with the spin density of the radical cation following one-electron
427 removal (*Figure 4B*), support the assignment of the experimentally observed oxidation peak. This
428 peak is therefore attributed to an oxidation process primarily localized within the aromatic ring of

429 the E2 molecule, ultimately corresponding to the oxidation of the phenolic hydroxyl group.

430
431 **Figure 4.** A) HOMO and LUMO of E2; B) Electron (spin) density of E2 corresponding radical
432 cation; C) Plot of the Fukui function towards nucleophilic (f_j^+) attack.

433
434 **Figure 4C** presents the plot of the Fukui function [34], illustrating the local reactivity of E2 at each
435 point in space toward nucleophilic attack. The analysis indicates that the region's most susceptible
436 to nucleophilic attack by a water molecule are the *ortho* and *meta* positions of the aromatic ring
437 relative to the hydroxyl group. The computed atomic Fukui indices (Table S1) identify C18 as the
438 most reactive site, suggesting it is the most likely to undergo a nucleophilic attack by H₂O
439 molecule. This hypothetical reaction, followed by further oxidation, would result in the formation
440 of a quinone-like adduct of E2.

441 Drawing from the insights garnered through our theoretical investigation, we propose two potential
442 oxidation pathways, as illustrated in Scheme 1. In both proposed mechanisms, oxidation occurs on
443 the aromatic ring and is initiated by electron removal from the phenolic moiety. In the first and
444 more probable pathway, the phenolic group undergoes irreversible oxidation to a ketone, and a
445 new conjugated system is established. In the alternative mechanism, following the initial oxidation
446 step, a water molecule performs a nucleophilic attack on the aromatic core, forming a catechol-
447 like analogue of E2. This intermediate is subsequently oxidized to a quinone-like derivative of E2.

448 The resulting product would be susceptible to reduction, leading to the regeneration of the catechol
449 adduct. However, the absence of a reduction peak in the experimental voltammogram supports the
450 first oxidation pathway as the more likely and dominant process. The results obtained under the
451 applied experimental conditions (scan rate $5\text{-}50\text{ mVs}^{-1}$) indicate the presence of a single anodic
452 peak, corresponding to a two-electron transfer process. This observation implies that the second
453 electron transfer occurs so rapidly following the first that the intermediate species cannot be
454 individually detected. The proposed oxidation mechanism is consistent with previously reported
455 findings [35-36].

456
457

Scheme 1. Proposed oxidation mechanisms of E2, determined by DFT.

458 *E2 determination using SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO*

459 Square wave voltammetry (SWV) was selected as the preferred method for E2 determination due
460 to its excellent resolution, high sensitivity and low background currents [37-39]. The method
461 parameters were systematically optimized to achieve a broad calibration range with a maximum
462 slope, ensuring optimal sensitivity for E2 measurement. During the optimization process, each
463 parameter was varied individually while keeping all others constant. The final SWV conditions
464 were determined based on the analyte's well-defined peak shape and maximum peak current, with
465 a pulse amplitude of 20 mV, a frequency of 10 Hz, and a potential step of 8 mV.

466 The obtained SWV curve shows that the oxidation current increased with the addition of E2
467 concentration from 0.1 to 30 μM . A shift in the oxidation peak potential at higher concentrations
468 was also observed, further confirming the previously mentioned explanation of analyte adsorption

469 on the electroactive surface (**Figure 5A**). A linear relationship between the oxidation peak currents
 470 and concentrations is represented with the following equation: $I (\mu\text{A}) = 0.04 + 0.1273 \times [\text{E2}]$ with
 471 $R^2 = 0.994$. Furthermore, the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) of the
 472 SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor were evaluated by using Eq. 7 and 8:

$$473 \quad LOD = \frac{3 \times \delta}{s} \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

$$474 \quad LOQ = \frac{10 \times \delta}{s} \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

475 Where ‘ σ ’ represents the standard deviation of the blank signal and ‘ δ ’ corresponds to the slope of
 476 the calibration curve. The fabricated SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor demonstrated an impressive LOD
 477 of 0.06 μM and a limit of quantification (LOQ) of 0.236 μM . Additionally, the sensitivity,
 478 calculated as the ratio of the slope to the electroactive surface area, was found to be 2.44 $\mu\text{A} \mu\text{M}^{-1}$
 479 cm^{-2} . These findings confirm the exceptional sensing performance of the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO
 480 sensor for E2 detection. Furthermore, the LOD and sensitivity were compared with previously
 481 reported results (**Table 1**), where the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor showed highly satisfactory
 482 performance in comparison.

483 **Table 1.** Comparative analytical performances of various electrochemical sensors for E2 detection

Electrode	Technique	Linear range (μM)	LOD (nM)	Reference
G-ZnO/GCE	DPV	0.05-100	8.3	[40]
Pd/N-RGO/GCE	DPV	0.005-0.02	1.8	[41]
GNR/FS-Au-CA/CPE	DPV	0.1-50	7.4	[42]
RGO/CuTthP/GCE	DPV	0.1-10	5.3	[43]
Cu(LNO ₂) ₂ /rGO/SPCE	LSV	2-42	53	[44]
CBGC	DPV	0.15-3.5	92	[45]
Al ₂ O ₃ /GCE	LSV	0.4-40	80	[46]
RGO-DHP/GCE	LSV	0.4-10	77	[47]
Fe ₃ O ₄ NPs-BMI.PF ₆ /CPE	SWV	0.1-10	50	[48]
Eu ₂ O ₃ @rGO/ SPCE	SWV	0.1-30	60	<i>This work</i>

484
 485 The comparative analysis reveals that the sensor developed in this study demonstrates comparable
 486 or superior performance for the evaluated electroanalytical parameters. The proposed method and
 487 the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor stand out for their advantages, including the use of low-cost
 488 materials for nanocomposite synthesis, a straightforward synthesis process, rapid fabrication of
 489 working electrodes, and an eco-friendly approach. As the electrode preparation process does not

490 involve the use of biological species such as antibodies or enzymes, the developed sensor offers
491 significant stability and resistance to external condition needed for straightforward on-site sensing.
492 Furthermore, it presents a promising opportunity for transitioning the proposed approach from
493 laboratory research to commercial applications.

494 ***Impact of potential interfering substances on sensor performance***

495 The selectivity of the proposed electrode of SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO was investigated by SWV in
496 BRBS at pH 4. This selectivity study was performed in 10 μM of E2 with ten times higher
497 concentrations than different interfering compounds, generally present in real samples, which
498 could potentially affect the sensor performance: Mg²⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, NO₃⁻, Ca²⁺, Cu²⁺, NO₂⁻, SO₄²⁻,
499 ascorbic acid, dopamine, caffeine, threonine, and uric acid. After the addition of dopamine,
500 ascorbic acid, and uric acid, due to their oxidation at similar potentials, a shift in the oxidation
501 peak current was observed; however, the current value remained unaffected. **Figure 5C** shows a
502 change in the current signal of less than 10% in the presence of interfering substances at
503 concentrations ten times higher than that of the target analyte. The selectivity studies demonstrated
504 that the oxidation current of E2 remained unaffected by any interfering species, highlighting the
505 SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor's exceptional selectivity for E2 detection.

506 ***Evaluating the repeatability, reproducibility, and storage stability of the proposed sensor***

507 The reproducibility and repeatability of the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor were evaluated using the
508 SWV method in BRBS (pH 4) containing 10 μM of E2. Repeatability was tested by performing
509 five consecutive measurements with the same SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor (**Figure 5D**), yielding a
510 relative standard deviation of 3.59%. Similarly, reproducibility was assessed by fabricating five
511 separate SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensors (**Figure 5E**), resulting in a relative standard deviation of
512 3.46%. The stability of the proposed sensor was further evaluated using SWV in the presence of
513 10 μM E2 at pH 4.0, throughout 1 to 30 days (specifically on the 1st, 7th, 10th, 15th, and 30th
514 days), as illustrated in **Figure 5F**. A relative standard deviation (RSD) of 4.06% was obtained,
515 confirming that the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor exhibits excellent storage stability. These results
516 demonstrate the reliability and robustness of the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor, emphasizing its
517 potential as a promising nanocomposite for selective and sensitive E2 detection in real-world
518 applications.

519
 520 **Figure 5.** **A)** SWV response of the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor with different concentrations of E2
 521 (0.1–30 μM) in BRBS (pH 4.0); **B)** A linear relationship between the oxidation peak currents and
 522 E2 concentrations; **C)** The bar graph of the relative inaccuracy (%) of current vs interfering
 523 molecules; **D)** SWV signal of five consecutive repeatability studies in the presence of 10 μM E2;
 524 **E)** SWV signal of reproducibility study in the presence of 10 μM E2; **F)** SWV indicates storage
 525 stability performance for 1-30 days in the presence of 10 μM E2.

526 **Real sample analysis**

527 The developed SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor was used to detect estradiol (E2) in tap water, river
 528 water, and saliva samples to demonstrate its practical applicability. The E2 content in these
 529 samples was analyzed using the proposed square wave voltammetry (SWV) method, with UV-Vis
 530 spectrometry employed as a validation technique. Three different E2 concentrations (5, 10, and 15
 531 μM) were spiked into each sample. Based on the obtained voltammograms (**Figure 6A-D**), peak
 532 current intensities, and calibration curves, the E2 concentrations were determined. These values
 533 were compared to the spiked concentrations, and recovery percentages were calculated (**Table 2**).

534

535 **Figure 6.** SWV current response for E2 detection in **A)** saliva sample 1, **B)** saliva sample 2 **C)** tap
 536 water, **D)** river water over SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO developed sensor

537 To further verify the method's accuracy, UV-Vis spectrometry was employed for E2 determination
 538 in the same samples (**Figure S4 A-D**). The results obtained with the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor
 539 closely matched those from the UV-Vis validation method, confirming the reliability and accuracy
 540 of the proposed approach (**Table 2**). Human saliva samples labeled as sample 1 and sample 2
 541 exhibit slightly lower recovery values when spiked with 10 μM, likely due to potential matrix
 542 effects. The results obtained with the SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor closely matched those from the
 543 UV-Vis validation method, confirming the reliability and accuracy of the proposed approach
 544 (**Table 2**).

545

546 **Table 2.** Results for E2 determination in spiked samples utilizing SPCE/Eu₂O₃@rGO sensor, using
 547 SWV method, and UV-Vis validation method.

Sample	Found (μM)	Added (μM)	Found (μM) SWV method	Recovery (%)	Found (μM) UV-Vis method
Tap water	/	5	4.99	99.85	4.81
		10	9.12	91.25	10.39
		15	16.00	106.69	14.76
River water	/	5	4.56	91.2	4.97
		10	9.05	90.48	9.54
		15	16.09	107.26	15.03
Human saliva sample 1	/	5	4.93	98.54	4.57
		10	8.56	85.65	9.08
		15	15.35	102.37	15.03
Human saliva sample 2	/	5	4.88	97.60	4.88
		10	8.79	87.92	9.10
		15	15.37	102.51	14.83

548 **Conclusion**

549 In this work, ultrafine europium oxide particles were synthesized by the hydrothermal method,
 550 which were further used to form a composite with synthesized reduced graphene oxide. This
 551 achieved a synergistic effect of both nanomaterials, resulting in excellent electrocatalytic
 552 capabilities of the newly formed composite. The morphological characteristics examined using
 553 advanced spectroscopic methods indicated the uniform structure of the nanomaterial. Moreover,
 554 the electrochemical characteristics of the obtained composite showed outstanding results. Finally,
 555 the composite was used to modify a screen-printed carbon electrode, which showed excellent
 556 electrocatalytic capabilities toward detecting the endocrine disruptor estradiol. Enviably results
 557 were achieved in the analytical performance of the designed sensor, which showed a detection
 558 limit of only 0.06 μM and a wide linear operating range from 1 to 30 μM. Other parameters of the
 559 analytical method, such as repeatability (3.59 %), reproducibility (3.46 %), and stability (over 30
 560 days), showed excellent results. When the sensor was used to monitor the concentration of
 561 estradiol in two different aqueous real water samples and two different human saliva samples, its
 562 excellent analytical performances were confirmed. Furthermore, a comprehensive quantum
 563 chemical analysis has been conducted to clarify the redox behavior of estradiol, offering a robust
 564 theoretical framework that supports the interpretation of experimental findings. Overall, the novel

565 sensor is a promising analytical tool for routine estradiol detection and monitoring, with excellent
566 predispositions for further modification towards disposable and point-of-need applications.

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